

A CRITICAL APPRAISAL OF QUESTIONNAIRE AND MIXED-METHOD RESEARCH IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the quality assessment of the questionnaire survey and the mixed methodology of the primary studies' in library and information science. Internet search strategies and meta-analyses were used to search the relevant literature in December 2023 based on the required word in the four databases. This study covered papers published during the years 2010–2023 on “use of electronic resource in medical libraries”. The PRISMA guidelines by Moher et al. (2009), a quality checklist for the questionnaire survey by Boynton and Greenhalgh (2004), and a quality checklist for mixed methodology by Mays et al. (2001) were applied. Results reveal that majority of the studies fulfill the quality assessment criteria about questionnaire survey; demonstrated clear research questions, questionnaires are understandable and used appropriate research design. The instrument covered all relevant aspects of the problem and used open-ended and closed-ended questions appropriately. Response rates have been given, coding and analysis were appropriate, and the presentation of results was good. In contrast, some studies did not frame the sample size in terms of population, did not mention the justification of reliability and validity for their instrument, pilot testing, and no evidence of ‘data dredging’ respectively. The studies of Devi and Keshava (2020), and Habib et al., (2022) fulfill most of the quality assessment criteria designed for questionnaire surveys. In addition, a study by Brennan et al. (2014) covered the maximum parameters of the quality checklist for mixed methodology and got 19 out of 21. In Addition, majority of the studies were written by two authors and covered medical students, faculty, and doctors as a population. India was reported to have conducted the most studies, followed by Nigeria and Saudi Arabia, and the year 2014, followed by 2017, 2019, and 2016, was the year of the most study publications. This study helps the researcher (s) to structure research papers on the basis of standardized criteria for questionnaire surveys and mixed methodology. This study also benefits the journal editor(s) in developing assessment criteria for the article.

INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of electronic resources has transformed the landscape of academic and medical

libraries, reshaping how knowledge is accessed, disseminated, and applied in both clinical and

academic settings. Medical libraries, in particular, have seen a rapid integration of databases, e-journals, online textbooks, clinical decision support tools, and other digital platforms aimed at supporting evidence-based practice, research, and education (Ukwueze et al., 2025). As the use of these resources continues to expand, understanding patterns of utilization, user satisfaction, barriers to access, and the overall impact on learning and clinical decision-making becomes essential for librarians, administrators, and policy-makers (Onwukanjo, 2017).

To capture these dynamics, researchers have increasingly employed questionnaire surveys and mixed-method research designs in their investigations. Questionnaire survey and mixed methodology studies are commonly used in social science especially in library and information sciences research to collect data from population or large samples of individuals (Bahader, 2022; Bahader, 2023). These methods can provide valuable insights to the attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors of a population and are often used to inform policy and decision-making (Fowler, 2013). However, the quality of the data collected through questionnaire surveys and mixed methodology depends largely on the quality of the paper structure and format (Bahader et al, 2020; Bahader et al., 2021). However, the quality and methodological rigor of these studies vary significantly. Issues such as poorly constructed survey instruments, lack of validity and reliability measures, inadequate sampling strategies, weak integration of qualitative and quantitative components, and insufficient reporting standards compromise the credibility of findings and limit their applicability. Therefore, it is precautiously essential to assess the quality of these research papers to ensure that the results are accurate, reliable, and valid. For this purpose the checklists for questionnaire designed by Boynton and Greenhalgh (2004) and for mixed methodology by Mays et al. (2001) were applied.

Despite the abundance of such studies in the field of library and information science, there is a noticeable gap in the systematic evaluation of their methodological soundness. Without critical appraisal, stakeholders risk making decisions based on flawed or incomplete evidence. This research, therefore, seeks to address this gap by conducting a structured and critical appraisal of primary studies focused on electronic resource use in medical libraries, with a

specific emphasis on two commonly used research designs: questionnaire surveys and mixed-method approaches.

To infer, this report will for sure help and assist researchers and scholars in the filed social sciences or library and information sciences in conducting high-quality questionnaire survey and mixed method studies. Ultimately, it will help in ensuring the data collected through these methods is reliable and can be used to inform policy and decision-making in variety of settings.

The study is guided by the following research questions:

RQ1: To what extent do the studies meet the quality assessment criteria tailored for questionnaire surveys?

RQ2: To what extent do the studies adhere to the quality assessment criteria devised for mixed methodology?

RQ3. What are statistics regarding demographic variables of the studies.

1. Methodology and Procedure

The current study adopted the internet search strategies and techniques to search the relevant literature which include specific steps and procedure including designing the research question, selecting the keywords for searching, selecting the relevant databases, retrieving the data from search engines based on predefined criteria, the critical appraisal of the selected studies, and presentation of the results. This study strictly followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis PRISMA guidelines (Liberati, 2009 & Moher, 2015).

Search Strategy

The literature was searched in four databases with query having two key words i.e. "Use of Electronic Resources" AND "Medical Library". Boolean Operator 'AND' was used in order to broaden the search results. Furthermore, the search was limited to title and abstract of the studies. The literature was searched on four well-known databases, i.e., Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science, and PubMed, a medical database. The search was conducted at the University of Peshawar, Peshawar using a Higher Education Commission (HEC) digital library in 2023. Some literature was also found with the help of

backward and forward citation searches. The details of the search strategies are given in the table 1.

Inclusion Criteria

- Only English-language research articles and studies have been published and determined the use of electronic resources in medical libraries were considered for this review.
- Papers published during the years 2010 to 2023 were included.
- Journal articles, conference papers, research theses and dissertations were included.
- No geographic restrictions were applied during search.
- Studies conducted on respondents associated to medical field (medical students, doctors, teachers, nurses, paramedics’ staff, etc.) were included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Studies published in languages other than English.
- Studies that did not use these terms like use, utilization, electronic resources or electronic information resources, user, in medical libraries" in either the title or abstract.
- Studies that only focused on electronic resources as a whole and did not discuss their utilization in medical libraries.
- Books were not included because the researchers felt that the length, methodologies, and assessment tools of monographs and research articles are different.
- Publication like book chapter, notes, news, reviews, summaries of oral presentations, summaries of posters, opinions, summaries of conferences, letters, editorials, fact sheets, errata, or citations.
- Articles published from before 2010.

Table 1: Search strategy and results

Database	Search strategy	Fields	Results
Google Scholar	“use of electronic resources” AND “medical library”	Title, Abstract	1010
Web of Science	“use of electronic resources” AND “medical library”	Title, Abstract	79
Scopus	“use of electronic resources” AND “medical library”	Title, Abstract	206
PubMed	“use of electronic resources” AND “medical library”	Title, Abstract	143
Total Results			1438

Validity and Reliability

The results were reported only from high-quality studies with no evidence of publication bias. The analysis and synthesis of the selected articles were carried out by the panel of experts. Each article was individually examined and analyzed, till an agreement was reached about an article. The authors tried their best to reduce errors and bias, hence, independently cross-checked each included article. Most of the studies reviewed had a consistent focus on the use of electronic resources in medical libraries around the globe. To increase inter-rater reliability during the literature analysis, this literature review was carried out by four researchers, and all of the procedures were discussed and compared before and after the review. The authors adopted Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines Moher et al. (2009) while conducted the SLR. The diagram (Figure1) clearly outlines all stages of the procedure: databases consulted, documents

collected and removed at each stage of the procedure, and the reasons for their removal at various stages of the systematic review.

Filtering

This inquiry was launched with 1438 papers in the first rehearsal of the search query. Articles were filtered by reviewing the title and abstract of the studies. The studies were reviewed according to pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria in order to reduce the probability of bias. The irrelevant and duplicate papers were removed. Figure1 shows the papers selected after a five-stage filtering process. A total of 47 studies were related, of which only 26 provided direct evidence to answer the research question of the study. Information was extracted from each eligible study in a specified form Figures (2, 3, & 4), and Appendices (A & B). The six parameters of quality assessment for the questionnaire survey and 15 parameters of quality assessment for the mixed

methodology of the studies were assessed. In addition, information were also extracted from each study

consisted of the author name(s), year of publication, country, respondents, methodology.

The PRISMA Diagram

Four phased flow diagram of studies selection procedure.

The PRISMA Diagram

Figure1. Flow chart of records retrieved, screened and included in the SLR based on the PRISMA approach (Moher et al., 2009).

Quality Appraisal

There exist numerous quality assessment checklists (QACs) that determine the quality of the manuscripts for review, and these can be changed or modified keeping in view the nature or need of study as most of them are developed and published in health care literature (Khan et al., 2011). Each included study in this review was independently reviewed by the researchers using a "quality checklist for questionnaire survey" developed by Boynton & Greenhalgh (2004). This checklist provides a standardized method for the evaluation of studies that used questionnaire surveys.

The quality appraisal of the articles was performed with regard to the six aspects of each article including (1) research question and design (2) sampling (3) instrument (4) response (5) coding and analysis (6) presentation of results respectively. Similarly, for studies having mixed method approach, the "quality checklist for mixed-methodology" developed by Mays et al. (2001) was used which examine the studies with 15 parameters including theresearch questions, design, funding, resource system, innovation, context, user system, dissemination mechanism, implementation

mechanism, sampling, data collection, data analysis, results, conclusions and reflexivity.

2. Results of the Study

Quality Assessment of the Studies for Questionnaire Surveys (RQ1)

All the included studies were evaluated in the light of parameter known as "quality checklist for questionnaire survey" specially designed by Boynton & Greenhalgh (2004) which evaluates the six main areas of the paper. The results in (Appendix A) shown that out of 23 studies, 13 studies got 9 score each out of 13 points which is 69% and five studies got 10 score each out of 13 points. The majority of the studies had clear research questions and only two studies' research designs were not suitable for study. Most of the studies did not taken data from the sample and did not frame the sample size for data collection. Only eight studies framed the sample size and collected data from the sample as population. Most of the questionnaire terminologies were understandable by the respondents. Majority of the studies lacked reliability and validity for the questionnaire and do not given Chromack alpha value. They do not conduct pilot testing of the questionnaire before conducting their final study. However, all questions in the questionnaire cover all relevant aspects of the problem, and open-ended and closed-ended questions were appropriately used. Response rate data have been given in all the studies except two. All studies utilized the correct techniques for data analysis and run appropriate tests for quantitative and qualitative data analysis. For the accuracy of the data, adequate measures were maintained in all studies. All the studies have reported relevant results, significant and non-significant and there is no evidence of 'data dredging' i.e. analyses that were not 'hypothesis driven' in all studies.

Quality Assessment of the Studies for Mixed-Methodology (RQ2)

Studies that employed Mixed Method were analyzed as per the "quality checklist for mixed methodology" by Mays et al., (2001) which evaluates with fifteen main areas of the papers. The results shown in (Appendix B), Brennan et al., (2014) study got 19 maximum score each out of 21 points which is 90%. This paper has research questions that were clearly

defined. The research design was appropriate for the study, which was funded by the South West Strategic Health Authority and the MEDEV mini-project scheme. In this study, the innovation sources were not mentioned; however, have an innovative idea regarding the utilization of e-resources. The context of the study was defined and linked results with previous studies. Beneficiaries of this study were mentioned, and it was also market. This study included sufficient cases/settings/observations; the data collection process was systematic; the data were analyzed systematically and rigorously; disconfirming observations were deleted; and the results were good, interesting, and meet the study objectives. The authors draw a clear link between data and explanation, and the authors' positions and roles are not clearly explained, and there are no ethical reservations about the study.

Similarly, studies by Ahmed and Al-Reyae (2017) and Scott et al., (2017) got a maximum score of 17 out of 21 points which is 81%. The research questions were clearly defined and design was appropriate for the study. The innovation sources were not mentioned; however, this study has an innovative idea regarding the utilization of e-resources. The context of the study was defined and link results with previous studies. Beneficiaries of these articles were mentioned, and these were marketed. These studies included sufficient cases/settings/observations; the data collection process was systematic; data were analyzed systematically and rigorously; disconfirming observations were deleted; and the results were good, interesting, and meet the study objectives. The authors draw a clear link between data and explanation, and the authors' positions and roles are not clearly explained, and there are no ethical reservations about the studies.

Descriptive Statistics of the Studies Regarding Authorship, Methods, Research Approach, Year of Publication and Country (RQ3)

Results indicate that total 26 studies were selected for review in this study in which twenty-three studies applied quantitative research approach using questionnaire and three mixed methodologies. Majority of the papers covered medical students, faculty and doctors as a population but few covered paramedical science professionals, hematologists,

pharmacist, nurses, medical laboratory technologists, medical records officers etc. Furthermore, majority of

the studies were written by two authors, ten by three or more authors and five by single author (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Authorship of the papers

As far as country wise publication is concerned India was reported the leading country having ten studies being conducted in that field followed by Nigeria with four studies and Saudi Arabia with three studies. Similarly, USA, Australia, UK, and Pakistan each had two studies and Iran with only one study during the periods 2010 to 2023 on usage of e-resources in medical libraries (Figure 3).

Year wise data of the studies are recorded in which, five studies were conducted on the subject in 2014, followed by four studies in 2017 and 2019 and three in 2016. Two studies were published in the year of 2010, 2013, 2020, 2022 each and the year 2011 and 2015 has only one publication (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Country wise papers publication

Figure 4: Year wise papers publications

3. Discussions

This study sought to find out quality assessment of the studies applied questionnaire survey, and mixed methodology. The studies were analyzed as per the "quality checklist for questionnaire survey" by Boynton & Greemhalgh (2004), which evaluates six areas (research question and design, sampling, instrument, response, coding and analysis, presentation of results), and the "quality checklist for mixed methodology" by Mays et al., (2001), which evaluates fifteen parts of the paper, respectively. As per the checklist of Boynton & Greemhalgh (2004), five studies such as Anandhalli and Shakuntala (2014), Sohail and Alvi (2014), Baudains et al. (2013), Devi and Keshava (2020), and Habib et al., (2022) got 10 out of 13 score which is 77% and covered all quality checklist ingredients for a questionnaire survey except reliability and validity, pilot testing of the instrument, and evidence of 'data dredging' (i.e., analyses that were not 'hypothesis-driven'). In addition, most of the papers by Thanuskodi, (2010), Baro and Endouware (2011), Anyaoku, (2015), Al-Hazm, (2016), Azami et al., (2016), Snow et al., (2016), Vijayalakshmi, et al., (2017), Anasuya, (2017), Shashikala and Srinivasaragavan (2019), Girimallesh (2019), Santhanalakshmi and Veerachamy (2019), Wynter et al., (2019), Singh and Gupta (2020), Alabdulwahhab et al., (2021), Sadaf et al., (2022) obtained 9 out of 13 score which is 69% as per the "quality checklist for

questionnaire survey". These contain clear research questions and appropriate research design, covered the whole population in spite of sample size and the terms in the questionnaire were under stable to all population. Most of the papers did not determine the reliability and validity of the instrument; questions covered all relevant aspects of the problem, open-ended and closed-ended questions were used appropriately, and no pilot testing was conducted. These studies mentioned that the response rate, coding, and analysis were appropriate, all relevant results ('significant' and 'non-significant') have been reported, and there is no evidence of 'data dredging' (i.e., analyses that were not 'hypothesis-driven'). Similarly, results of the primary studies for quality assessment of mixed methodology, conducted by Brennan et al. (2014) got 19 out of 21 score which is 90%, covering all parameters of the checklist except for the resource system, immediate implementation mechanism, and the authors' positions and roles clearly explained. In addition, two papers such as Ahmed and Al-Reyae (2017) and Scott et al., (2017) secured 17 out of 21 scores which are 81%, covering all criteria for mixed methods except funding sources, resource systems, immediate implementation mechanisms, and the authors' positions and roles clearly explained, respectively. As far as statistics about the authorship, methods, research approach, year of publication, and country of

the studies are concerned, out of 26 studies, 11 were written by two authors, ten by three or more, and five by a single author. Twenty-three studies applied a quantitative research approach, using questionnaires as instruments and three mixed methodology. The majority of the papers covered medical students, faculty, and doctors as a population, but few covered paramedical science professionals, such as hematologists, pharmacists, nurses, medical laboratory technologists, medical records officers, etc. Self-developed questionnaires were used in all studies. India was reported at the top followed by Nigeria, USA, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Australia, and Iran.

4. Conclusions, Limitations, Implications and Recommendations

This study is based on a quality assessment of the studies using a questionnaire survey and mixed methodology. Findings about quality assessment for the questionnaire survey demonstrated that the majority of the studies had clear research questions that were important and sensible, used appropriate research design, and the questionnaires were understandable to respondents. The study's instrument covered all relevant aspects of the problem and used open-ended and closed-ended questions appropriately. Population response rate were given in the majority of the studies. All studies utilized the correct techniques for data analysis, ran the appropriate tests for quantitative and qualitative data analysis, and reported relevant results appropriately. In contrast, the majority of the studies did not frame the sample size, lacking justification of reliability and validity for their questionnaire and pilot testing, and there is no evidence of 'data dredging, i.e., analyses that were not 'hypothesis-driven. The most appropriate studies that used the questionnaire survey method and fulfilled the maximum level of the quality assessment criteria designed for questionnaire surveys are Anandhalli and Shakuntala (2014), Baudains et al. (2013), and Habib et al. (2022). In addition, a study by Brennan et al. (2014) covers the majority of parameters as per the checklist of quality assessment for mixed methodology and is recommended for guidance. The demographic data regarding authorship, methods, research approach, year of publication, and country of the studies were also find.

Results show that the majority of the studies were written by two authors, covered medical students, faculty, and doctors as a population, and used a self-developed questionnaire. Most studies were conducted in India, followed by Nigeria and Saudi Arabia, and most studies were published in 2014, followed by 2016, 2017, and 2019.

The author hopes that the findings of this study will promote the debate on the best methodology for assessing the quality of academic journals. This study will assist in ensuring that the studies followed standardized criteria are reliable and can be used to inform policy and decision-making in a variety of settings. It also helps to ensure the accuracy and completeness of the data collected and generalizability of the findings, and the data are triangulated effectively. This study will also help researchers and scholars in structuring their research papers on the basis of standardized criteria for questionnaire surveys and mixed methodology. It is recommended that every journal should follow the standardized rule and checklist of quality assessment for the questionnaire survey and mixed methodology before publishing an article. Researchers and scholars should structure their research papers on the basis of standardized criteria for questionnaire surveys and mixed methodology. Every research paper should calculate reliability and validity for their questionnaire and do pilot testing before formal data collection. Further research is needed to standardize these methods and overcome the factors that create distrust of their validity and reliability.

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Appendix A: Results of the Quality Checklist for Questionnaire Survey

Quality assessment of the studies for questionnaire survey								
S.NO.	Author, Year	1(out of 2)	2(out of 2)	3(out of 4)	4 (out of 1)	5 (out of 2)	6 (out of 2)	Total score (out of 13)
1	Oduwole & Oyewumi (2010)	1+0	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	8
2	Thanuskodi, (2010)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
3	Baro & Endouware (2011)	1+1	1+1	0+1+0+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
4	Adesoye & Amusa (2013)	1+0	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	8
5	Anandhalli & Shakuntala (2014)	1+1	1+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	10
6	Sohail & Alvi (2014)	1+1	1+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	10
7	Eagle et al. (2014)	0+1	1+1	0+1+1+0	0	1+1	1+0	8
8	Anyaoku, (2015)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
9	Al-Hazm, (2016)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
10	Azami et al., (2016)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
11	Snow et al., (2016)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
12	Baudains et al., (2016)	1+1	1+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	10
13	Vijayalakshmi, et al., (2017)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
14	Anasuya, (2017)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
15	Shashikala & Srinivasaragavan (2019)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
16	Girimalles (2019)	1+1	1+1	0+1+1+0	0	1+1	1+0	9
17	Santhanalakshmi & Veerachamy (2019)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
18	Wynter et al., (2019)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
19	Devi & Keshava (2020)	1+1	1+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	10
20	Singh & Gupta (2020)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
21	Alabdulwahhab et al., (2021)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9
22	Sadaf et al., (2022)	1+1	0+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	9

23	Habib et al., (2022)	1+1	1+1	0+1+1+0	1	1+1	1+0	10
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Quality assessment of the studies for questionnaire survey checklist: 1=Research questions & design score; 2= Sampling; 3= Instrument; 4= Response; 5= Coding and analysis; 6= Presentation of results (Total Score=13)

Appendix B: Results of the Quality Checklist for Mixed-Methodology

S.NO	Author, Year	Quality assessment of the studies for mixed methodology															Total score (out of 21)
		1 (out of 2)	2 (out of 1)	3 (out of 1)	4 (out of 1)	5 (out of 1)	6 (out of 2)	7 (out of 1)	8 (out of 1)	9 (out of 1)	10 (out of 1)	11 (out of 1)	12 (out of 2)	13 (out of 2)	14 (out of 2)	15 (out of 2)	
1	Brennan et al., (2014)	1+1	1	1	0	1	1+1	1	1	0	1	1	1+1	1+1	1+1	0+1	19
2	Ahmed & Al-Reyae, (2017)	1+1	1	0	0	1	1+1	1	1	0	1	1	1+1	1+1	1+1	0+1	17
3	Scott et al., (2017)	1+1	1	0	0	1	1+1	1	1	0	1	1	1+1	1+1	1+1	0+1	17

Quality assessment of the studies for mixed methodology checklist: 1=Questions; 2= Design; 3= Funding; 4= Resource system; 5=Innovation; 6= Context; 7= User system; 8= Dissemination mechanism; 9= Implementation mechanism; 10= Sampling; 11= Data collection; 12= Data analysis; 13= Results; 14= Conclusions; 15=Reflexivity.

